

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING TELECOMMUNICATION LEARNING PROJECTS IN INDEPENDENT EDUCATION

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***Abstract.** The article focuses on the importance and necessity of digitalization of independent education in the credit module system of higher education and the use of telecommunication educational projects. Information on the content, types and international projects of telecommunications educational projects is provided. The procedure for organizing project protection and its external evaluation criteria are explained.*

***Key words:** credit, module, system, project, telecommunication, international, evaluation, external evaluation.*

INTRODUCTION

The introduction of the credit-module system in the higher education system of Uzbekistan required a radical re-development of the curricula of educational areas and master's specialties. In the current credit-module system, 50-60% of the total educational load allocated to the major subjects in the curriculum of bachelor's education courses, and about 60-70% in the master's specializations are allocated to independent education. However, independent education is mainly carried out by preparing abstracts on the topic or giving tasks to summarize the topic. Writing an annotation or review on the topic can be added to this, and this will at least guide students to independent creative thinking. These traditional methods are outdated and do not work well in the innovative educational environment. Therefore, the author recommends organizing independent education in science based on digital technologies, that is, "Telecommunication educational projects", using the method of designing [1].

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Pedagogical observation, comparative analysis, generalization, pedagogical experiment-test, mathematical-statistical analysis, mental cards, expert survey of foresight, development of scenarios, future box, and Delphi methods were used in the research process.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Organization of telecommunications projects requires a certain amount of preparatory work. In this, for example, how to find partners to study a specific problem? - the question arises. For this, it is possible to find partners from foreign countries by referring to the IEARN (<http://www.iearn.org>) and KIDLINK (<http://www.kidlink.org>) programs mentioned above. Or, you can go to the professional cooperation sites of teachers: European cooperation (<http://www.eun.org>) or Russian (<http://www.ioso.ru/distant/communiity>) and propose the project to them. Of course, in any case it is required that teachers coordinate students' activities from both sides. It is also important to introduce partners here. To do this, project participants can send short information about themselves together with their photos so that partners on the site can get acquainted. Because knowing the interests of partners and with whom they work in general plays an important role in such communication [2].

When working with foreign partners, it is necessary to know their specific cultural and traditional values and treat them with respect. That's why it is necessary to organize correspondence in an extremely literate language, respectfully to the partner, in an off-line mode (via e-mail or forum) or on-line mode (chat). Especially for the language of communication (foreign language), it is necessary to organize a serious preliminary preparation, taking into account the socio-cultural characteristics and speech culture of the representatives of the partner country, and the advice of the coordinator is very necessary [3]. The organization of telecommunication projects is not only international, but also regional or within the framework of one country. Because there will be no language barrier in the organization of the project, but the condition of taking into account national and ethnic, socio-cultural values and treating them with respect remains. The defense of the project is organized first at each partner educational institution during the training, and then by posting their presentation materials on the forum or on the website of one of the educational institutions. Partners can ask questions in the forum about the presented materials and receive relevant answers [4].

Timely and correct organization of external evaluation of telecommunications projects is one of the main factors affecting project effectiveness and practicality of obtained results. Because this makes it possible to make the necessary corrections during the work process and project protection. The nature of the external assessment depends on the type of project, its topic, its content and the conditions of its implementation. If the telecommunication project is a research project and it is carried out in different stages, the overall result of the project will depend on the degree of correct organization of the stages. In this case, the evaluation does not have to be made

by a specific mark. If the project is being organized during training, it can be done with the help of various incentive methods or orientation instructions [5,6]. For example, "Everything is correct, continue", "It is necessary to stop here and think", "It does not fit for some reason, try to consult and discuss" and other similar expressions. In creative projects, there is often no opportunity to evaluate intermediate results. However, it is still necessary to monitor the work and provide help and guidance if required (of course, not as a ready-made solution, but as advice). External evaluation is necessary in the form of interim or final external evaluation and depends on many factors. The teacher should conduct continuous monitoring of the collaborative project process [7]. During the defense of the project, in order to evaluate its results, the most talented student or other teacher in this field is selected as an external expert. Or, at the beginning of the project, a special group of experts is formed to evaluate and monitor the work of different groups working on this project.

The following factors are taken into account in the external evaluation of the project:

- relevance and importance of the presented problem, compatibility of the studied topics with each other;
- appropriateness of used research methods and methods of processing obtained results;
- activity of each project participant according to personal capabilities;
- the collective nature of the decision to be made;
- sufficient and deep insight into the problem, possibility to use knowledge of other fields of science;
- treatment and mutual support of project participants, as well as mutual complements and corrections;
- to be able to prove the decisions made, justify their conclusions and results with evidence;
- aesthetics of presentation and presentation of project results;
- participants to answer the opponents' questions abilities, reasonableness of answers and proof based on evidence;
- ability to imagine the consequences of the decisions made.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, educational telecommunication projects are part of high pedagogical technologies and require a lot of preparation from both the teacher and the student, and serious coordination of the student's entire educational activity. At the same time, this technology helps to develop the student intellectually, to form critical and creative thoughts. Such systematic cooperative activity leads not only to the

formation of independence in young people, but also to an increase in their responsibility for their own work and team activities. Therefore, it is appropriate to consider educational telecommunication projects as one of the most effective methods in the field of education that meets the requirements of the modern educational system and to widely apply it to the educational process.

REFERENCES

1. Raximov O.D., Turgunov O.M. va b. Zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalari. /Toshkent, «Fan va texnologiyalar» nashriyoti, 2013y, 205b.
2. Prokopeva N.I. Proektnoe obuchenie v zarubezhnoy pedagogye. K voprosu o stanovlenii i razvitii //Sibirsky uchitel. 2004. No. 2. March-April. URL: www.websib.ru
3. Polat E.S., Novye pedagogicheskie i informatsionnye tehnologii v sistem obrazovaniya ed. E.S. Polat - M., 2004. Рахимов О.Д. Инновацион педагогик технологиялар: лойихалар услуби таълим сифатини оширувчи технология сифатида. / Қарши, ТАТУ Қарши филиали, 2013й.
4. Raximov O.D. Innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalar: loyihalar uslubi ta'lim sifatini oshiruvchi texnologiya sifatida. / Qarshi, TATU Qarshi filiali, 2013y.
5. What is a telecommunications project?
URL: <https://soc-work.ru/article/480>.
6. Telecommunication projects: organization and implementation.
URL: <https://studbooks.net/1872436/pedagogika/>
7. Telecommunication educational projects
URL: <https://studepedia.org/index.php?vol=3&post=29539>.